

[Gary Shteyngart's *Our Country Friends*: Idolatry of the Self in America and the Global Era]

Martín Urdiales Shaw

University of Vigo
Vigo, Spain

[Abstract] *Despite the communality invoked in its title words, Shteyngart's pandemic novel Our Country Friends (2021) presents several characters who are primarily identified by self-absorption, whether through solipsism, narcissism, egotism or competitiveness. The present article proposes a close reading of the human group presented in the novel as displaying these types of profiles, which socially and culturally originate in Christopher Lasch's classic assessment of narcissism in American culture (1979), profiles which, I argue, have today become intensified, both in the US and the First World at large, by the pervasive influence of a global neoliberal paradigm which celebrates unchecked individualism, the accumulation of wealth, and the commodification of the self.*

[Keywords] *narcissism; solipsism; competitiveness; digital technologies; authorship; neoliberalism; globalization; Our Country Friends*

Shteyngart's 2021 pandemic novel, *Our Country Friends*, is a manifest departure from his earlier hyperbolic satires, a work that, as reviewer Carlin Romano noted, is "still funny [as] if befits a pandemic novel, but not slapstick funny" (n.p.). Also unlike the writer's earlier fiction, *Our Country Friends* is composed as a choral, multi-perspective narrative, charting the discussions, reflections, arguments and "entanglements" among a middle-aged writer, his family and various friends during a protracted retreat in upstate New York, "offer[ing] real characters who resist simplification" (Romano, n.p.) Insofar as this is a work that hybridizes genres in significant ways, as Liliana Naydan has discussed at length (see "The Politics of Genre Migration", 307-324), the text is prefaced by the theatrical device of *dramatis personae*, listing the three Russian Jewish Senderovskys (writer husband Sasha, psychiatrist wife Masha, their child Nat), two high-school friends of the writer, the Korean Karen Cho, the Indian Vinod Mehta, Sasha's student Dee Cameron, and the wealthy traveler Ed Kim, also of Korean origin. They are later joined by the Actor, who is ostensibly working with Sasha on a script adaptation of his work. Shteyngart draws from his own life and personal circumstances,¹ projecting Sasha as an older, fading version of himself as a writer, while thematically drawing from two world classics, Boccaccio's *The Decameron* and Chekhov's *Uncle Vanya*,² in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic raging in New York and urban America during the summer of 2020.

Headed by Sasha and Masha Senderovsky, who represent a "new wave of gentrification ... of middle-class bohemians moving from increasingly unaffordable cities to the countryside" (review by Laura Miller, n.p.), the novel's cast of characters represents a variety of liberal outlooks, which range from the artistic or intellectual to the entrepreneurial and affluent. Liliana Naydan has perceptively discussed how the novel's "colony of immigrant characters" functions as a "microcosm of twenty-first-century America" (310) in setting this progressive group against the backdrop of local farmland surroundings where WASP / Republican / redneck residents seem to be the norm.³ *Our Country Friends* is in part, a novel of its particular context, specifically the first Trump presidency and its disastrous response to the Covid-19 crisis, or the racial tensions triggered in the wake of the George Floyd murder, in May 2020. However, it is not my priority here to read this text politically, but rather to explore an angle that has been mostly overlooked in earlier discussions that have insisted more on American political divisiveness and the immigrant narrative – namely that, with one exception, the characters in Senderovsky's bungalow colony conform, in psychological terms, to a variety of modes of self-absorption, solipsism and narcissism that emerge, and result, from twenty-first century American life and the prospects that the global neoliberal era offers the wealthy.

[1] Living from Legacy: Solipsistic Ed Kim

The wealthiest of Senderovsky's guests is Ed Kim, who is listed in the *Dramatis Personae* as "A gentleman", in mocking reference to the 19th century dramaturgical convention to identify aristocrats or members of the nobility. In the context of global neoliberalism, Ed is certainly a "contemporary gentleman", identified later as "a scion of a *chaebol* family"

– a term that in the South Korean context identifies a reduced number of very wealthy families who own large industrial conglomerates (Samsung and the like). Indeed, Ed does not need to work for a living, and besides his South Korean family origins, he has secured Swiss, British and Canadian citizenships, his sole occupation up to the pandemic having been to travel constantly in business class visiting his wealthy peers, “similarly situated friends around the world” (*Friends* 16). His brother has bought a vineyard in Hungary, and his mother, whose housemaid has packed Ed’s luggage, lives in Gangnam, the most expensive Seoul district, which became globally known through Korean pop singer PSY’s music hit “Gangnam Style” in 2012.⁴ His sojourn at the Senderovsky estate, in the context of the pandemic’s ban on air travel, is frequently employed by Shteyngart to foreground Ed’s elitism and haughtiness, usually displayed in his epicurean proclivities: he is a gourmet and a wine connoisseur. Sasha’s initial shopping round is troubled by his attempts to avoid overspending, yet he buys some expensive European wines, as “Ed ... would be the hardest to accommodate ... he could picture [him] pursing his lips around a glass and pronouncing it ‘drinkable’” (*Friends* 5). Later, as the two shop together at Rudolph’s Market, Sasha is alarmed by the overpriced “international” products, “which Ed carelessly piles into a basket” (*Friends* 12). In a number of ways – unlimited wealth, international contacts, multiple citizenships – Ed Kim is modeled on an earlier Shteyngart character, the protagonist of *Absurdistan* Misha Vainberg (there Misha’s wealth has corrupt origins), as both exemplify what the Slovenian philosopher Slavok Žižek termed “the free-floating global elite” (quoted in Lee, 31), men of family wealth, privileged education and refined tastes, free from any income-related anxieties.

Like many of Shteyngart’s characters who are free from the ordinary struggles of life, Ed, who has known Sasha since their twenties, displays a narcissistic nature which is explicitly antisocial and even borders on the autistic. Just arrived, he envisions the sojourn at the Sasha estate as a period of “boredom on the horizon, of endless upper-middleclass chatter, badly made country Negronis, cigarettes snuck” (*Friends* 10) – and his first greeting of Sasha’s wife is contrived, guided by a performative display of politeness: “He knew he had to get some preliminaries out of the way. ‘Thank you so much for hosting me during this time. It’s much appreciated. He forced himself to take an exaggerated breath of damp air. ‘Mmm,’ he said. ‘Just what the surgeon general ordered’” (*Friends* 12). Ed is essentially a self-proclaimed loner who is, at heart, sceptical about friendship (“Be strong for his friends? Velocity was his friend. Disappearing landscapes were his friends,” *Friends* 17) and who suffers from a nervous tic at times of social anxiety, covering his right ear with a cupped hand. Shteyngart makes extensive use of male autism in his earlier novel *Lake Success*,⁵ and Ed Kim’s repeated gesture in *Our Country Friends* (covering his ear/s) is evocative of an action known as ‘stimming’ in autistic individuals, a self-soothing behaviour that can help regulate emotions and provide a sense of comfort.

[2] The Lone Digital Guru: Karen Cho

Another of Senderovsky's friends with Korean origins, "slightly related to Ed through a dissipated ancestor back in Seoul," (*Friends* 19) is Karen Cho, a brilliant entrepreneur whose recent personal crises contrast with her professional triumph. In this novel, Karen epitomizes Shteyngart's critique of contemporary techno-capitalism, a theme that looms larger in his earlier novel *Super Sad True Love Story*. Karen is a digital guru who has got rich quick by developing *Tröö Emotions*, a ragingly popular smartphone app that causes people to fall in love by algorithmically processing a user's picture looking into another user's eyes. Shteyngart cleverly escalates the smartphone narcissism of his dystopian *Super Sad True Love Story* into a shared mode, one that goes beyond self-absorption. Whether scientifically "true" or a mere placebo – this remains unresolved – *Tröö Emotions* blends the digital narcissism of the selfie with the commodification of the emotional (loving) self, problematizing Jonathan Franzen's notion, originally delivered as a commencement address, that "the world of techno-consumerism is ... troubled by real love, and it has no choice but to trouble love in return" (Franzen, WK 10). Ironically, but perhaps also expectedly, Karen Cho is portrayed as a lonely woman who has always found it difficult to secure love. Recently divorced, and since the success of the *Tröö Emotions* app estranged from her younger sister and from her elderly father, her persistent memories of childhood involve finding solitary refuge in her upstairs room from the domestic quarrels of her immigrant parents. In the present, upon her arrival at the bungalow colony, she is the first to locate Natasha ("Nat"), the Senderovskys' child whom the parents had been anxiously missing for a time in the colony grounds. Karen immediately establishes an emotional bond with Nat, becoming "Karen-emo" to her (Korean for "auntie Karen") and adopting a foster-parent role with the girl, by creating a complicity that is partly based on Korean language and popular culture. Their complicity escalates to the point of generating resentment in Masha Senderovsky: "Karen was now teaching her daughter another language. There was nothing inherently wrong with that, except maybe she could have consulted her. [...] She wanted Karen out of her sight" (*Friends* 130).

Karen's stay at the bungalow colony is also emotionally burdened by her nostalgia for happier times in her youth, as another of her and Senderovsky's high-school friends, the Indian Vinod Mehta, has been invited to stay. As Karen has always known, Vinod, whose story among the "country friends" is the most tragic (having survived lung cancer and abandoned an academic career) has always loved her, but Karen is unable to reciprocate Vinod's feelings in a romantic way. During an evening of heavy drinking and joint smoking with her male friends – Senderovsky, Vinod and Ed – Karen reminisces:

[she] felt the years falling away. When she reached for her glass on the side table, she could have been reaching for a carafe of cheap Beaujolais at their favourite restaurant back in the day. A brasserie named Florent, the chrome-edged fortress of their origin story. Now she was scared of time's compression, scared of the innocence Vinod invoked. They kept telling her that now, and only now, her life finally

attained “limitless possibilities.” But all of these possibilities seemed quite limited, and asterisked besides, born of unexercised stock options, but not the understanding of others. The trajectory was clear: every passing year would mean being more alone... (*Friends* 72)

Karen's contemporary life as a middle-aged smart tech executive is plagued by loneliness and the absence of “true love”: in Shteyngart's dark irony of our times, she has counteracted such an absence by means of her groundbreaking business idea, the design of a smartphone app, “Tröö Emotions”, that invokes and resignifies Puck's love potion in Shakespeare's *A Midsummer Night's Dream* within the parameters of the digital era. And yet Karen longs for love and affection in the most traditional sense, as she later fantasizes about having a real, tangible, family made up of Vinod and Senderovsky's daughter: “She could take her somewhere, Karen thought. Somewhere far away. Two sisters making a life together. The plan built in her mind like a storm. And Vinod? Could she love a man she pitied? But what if she no longer pitied him?” (*Friends* 139).

[3] Celebrity Roles, Celebrity Rules: The Actor

One character remains deliberately unnamed, as indicative of mainstream American culture's veneration of celebrity status: the “Actor.” In a bungalow colony composed mostly of gentrified immigrants, “the Actor [is] a non-immigrant insider to American culture because of his language, his nationality, and his apparently white race” (Naydan 313). The attractive Actor becomes the main disruptive force: he stirs everyone's awareness, and the sexual interest of all three women, who each have individual masturbatory fantasies with him at one point in the novel. He is by far the most narcissistic and self-absorbed individual: although his own television career reveals dubious artistic talent, he systematically patronizes Sasha and derides his skill as a writer. In one of his several disputes with Senderovsky regarding the adaptation of the writer's⁶ script, the actor admits: “Yes, I'm self-entitled, [...] but that's what drew me into this role [of Misha] to begin with. It's the most natural elucidation of who I am as a person circa right now. It's the rare role that lets me plunge feet first into myself” (*Friends* 94). In discussing the Actor in relation to performativity in this “genre-crossing” novel, Liliana Naydan draws on the writer's National Public Radio interview (conducted by Dave Davies, November 2021) to observe how this figure, like Barry Cohen in *Lake Success*, “is a commentary on ‘how in America we treat celebrities’ ... [and a] commentary on the elites of the United States” (313). It is worth noting that in this country, the relevance of ‘screen’ celebrity idols (actors, performers, comedians) in popular culture dates back to 1920s and 30s Hollywood cinema, but it continued to be a pervasive influence throughout the heyday of television shows in the 1950s and 60s, as it is still today, in our screen-dominated era when almost everything is audiovisual and can be streamed into smartphones anywhere. As has been noted, Shteyngart's choice to leave the actor unnamed throughout the novel⁷ is relevant in highlighting his typecast identity, a status that involves and signifies serious ethical shortcomings.

As the novel's plot unfolds, in its distinctive blend of American cultural commentary and classical Greek tragedy, the Actor, through his selfish and self-serving acts, becomes an agent of doom for the characters in the bungalow retreat who are most intellectual and most removed from the late-capitalist success ethic. Accordingly, his irresponsible actions shape the fates of both Dee Cameron and Vinod Mehta. Videotaped by a stalker, his sexual encounter with Dee on a derelict open-air stage at a children's camp goes viral on the internet, becoming rapidly manipulated to discredit her promising career as an essayist through various twisted accusations,⁸ as hate posts in social media escalate blaming her for the Actor's infidelity to his (public) fiancée. This incident, once it goes viral, triggers the Actor's furtive flight from the colony at the request of his agent, who calls in to warn: "You are not just a 'person' ... You are a responsibility onto this world" (*Friends* 207). The agent's words resonate with superb irony, when on the Actor's unexpected – and unwelcome – return to the bungalow colony weeks later, he now carries the Covid-19 infection that will eventually bring about Vinod Mehta's death.

[4] Narcissism, Rivalry and Cancellation

Within Shteyngart's skeptical vision of contemporary narcissism in the US and the First World, it is symbolically appropriate that Vinod Mehta becomes the only victim of the pandemic in *Our Country Friends*, despite the apparent safety of the secluded bungalow colony. His death signifies his final defeat and his alienation from the narcissistic success drives of entrepreneurial America, which characters like the *Tröö Emotions* guru Karen or the Actor explicitly embody, but which have also been surreptitiously adopted by the host Sasha Senderovsky in his writerly ambitions. By American cultural standards the only "loser" of the group, Vinod was an adjunct professor who later adjusted to becoming a short-order cook. Significantly, he is also the most loyal, selfless and ethical character, the author of an unpublished novel of youth that was read only by Sasha, in whose judgement Vinod had placed his entire trust years earlier. Events in the novel gradually reveal that Sasha's past advice not to take the manuscript to a publisher was triggered by rivalry, at a time when Sasha still had to prove himself as a writer. Aware of its artistic quality, Sasha has immobilized the typewritten manuscript for years and even lies to Vinod about losing the box containing it, though in reality he has buried it in the bungalow colony's grounds,⁹ where it is accidentally discovered by his daughter Nat. This discovery becomes an epiphanic moment for Karen, who recollects begging the distraught Vinod to let her read the manuscript, as "Sasha [could] be a dick about other people's work" (*Friends* 101). In the present, Vinod's final discovery of the box and of Senderovsky's deceit leads to a desperate confrontation with his long-time friend and now host:

"Was it good?" Vinod shouted, "Was it? And then you lied to me because you're-you're-a fucking—" He was not sure could break the rules of their relationship, the three-decades-old established order of things: Karen at the top, Senderovsky by her side, Vinod orbiting whosoever gravitational pull was stronger at any given time.

“A fucking fraud!”, he finally shouted.

As Senderovsky looked into his friend's eye from the corner of his own, he thought:
My God, he's an adult now.

And: *This is the end of our family.*

“I'm sorry,” Senderovsky said, just as Karen flip-flopped onto the poorly lit stage of the porch, just as Vinod, using the hand that was not holding the remains of the Teva box, slapped Senderovsky with precisely felt fury across the left cheek.

(*Friends* 183-4)

Rather ironically, other textual expressions in *Our Country Friends* are subjected to (less radical) forms of cancellation. Senderovsky's collaboration with the Actor in developing a script for a television series from the writer's novel (see footnote 6) never really goes well, and at one point it leads the Actor to question Senderovsky's talent, in what emerges as a battle of egos:

“[...] Do you know what this script lacks, what all of your scripts lack? One word. Subtext.”

“I thought a graduate seminar on subtext,” Senderovsky said.

“That's your defence for a shitty script? Academia?”

The Actor launched into another soliloquy, this one more impassioned and the last...
(*Friends* 95)

While there is some poetic justice in Senderovsky being faced with cancellation, another kind of writer in the novel, Dee Cameron, receives abuse simply because of her sexual affair with the Actor, which has gone viral on social media. A personal essay, published online, about her childhood response to watching the “seminal American racist film” *Gone with the Wind* (Shteyngart here targets the narrow-mindedness of cancel culture in relation to classic texts), is now perversely decontextualized and scrutinized on social media to accuse her of alt-right racism: “to make matters worse, ... she had twice featured a racial epithet issuing from an uncle's mouth..., which now too was part of a screenshot next to ‘mypeople’ and ‘ShitDeeSays’” (*Friends* 197). Ultimately, Dee is not really victimized for her cultural or political views as expressed in her essay, but rather the divisive political climate of the United States is exploited by anonymous posters to incite hatred against her, in what emerges as a histrionic display of self-righteousness by the users themselves.

[5] Conclusions

Within Gary Sheyngart's fiction, *Our Country Friends* is his novel to date¹⁰ that best diagnoses how our era fosters and generates ego-driven personalities, certainly under the influence of contemporary American values and in the context of global neoliberalism. As early as 1979, years before pervasive global travel, obscure financial assets, cryptocurrencies and the emergence of the world wide web, in his book *The Culture of Narcissism*, Christopher Lasch cross-examined various facets of American life (social interactions,

business relations, sports and games, sexual behaviours, family life) to examine the prevalence of “pathological narcissism”¹¹ as follows: “the psychological patterns associated with pathological narcissism, which in less exaggerated form manifest themselves [...] in the fascination with fame and celebrity, the fear of competition, the inability to suspend disbelief, the shallowness and transitory quality of personal relations, [...], originate in the peculiar structure of the American family, which [...] originates in changing modes of production” (Lasch 176). Significantly, Lasch’s ideas on the transformation of American life in the sixties and seventies have now become relevant, perhaps to an even greater degree, to twenty-first century America, to first-world countries, and to the global neoliberal era at large. *Our Country Friends* is a nuanced and complex novel that stages the urbane dialogues, friendly complicities, nostalgic memories, informal banter and jokes, and even sexual relations among a group of characters who share worldly, liberal attitudes in a bungalow colony secluded from pandemic America. Yet at the same time, in doing so, it also reveals the most narcissistic and solipsistic drives that underlie the individuals in this group: the traveler Ed Kim’s epicurean elitism, Karen Cho’s solitude in her entrepreneurial success, Senderovsky’s egocentric personality as a writer, and the Actor’s vanity and disregard for others. All of them have created victims through their actions and behaviour. Two of these victims belong to and partake of the society of “friends” created at the bungalow colony: Vinod Mehta, who pays the highest price of all – his own life, having been infected with Covid-19 by the Actor – and Dee Cameron, who encounters the destruction of her social persona online, and probably the abrupt end of a promising writing career. Beyond the range of the novel, other unknown and anonymous victims are created, as Karen Cho profits from what Simon Willmetts has termed “digital dystopia” (272) by exploiting a “technology of power takes on subtle, supple and smart forms, [escaping] all visibility” (Han, *Psychopolitics* 14), while Ed Kim’s lighthearted, elitist consumerism is only possible due to his family’s prominent standing within the structures of corporate global capitalism.

It is ironic that Gary Shteyngart’s first choral novel – one that explicitly invokes communality in the words of its title and is not dominated by a single protagonist or narrative perspective – should showcase a cast of characters whose actions, deeds and words reveal in various ways the contemporary idolatry of the self, chiefly empowered by the dictates of worldwide contemporary neoliberalism. In a fundamental sense, these characters are very real people, and *Our Country Friends* is a very pertinent text in exposing how, in our global era, “liquid modernity has created a new and unprecedented setting for individual life pursuits [where] social forms and institutions no longer have enough time to solidify and cannot serve as frames of reference for human actions” (Bauman 1). And, of course, it also begs the grim question of where such a paradigm will eventually lead humankind in the future.

[Notes]

- 1 The bungalow colony is a magnified fictional recreation of the writer's actual bungalow in Dutchess County, New York, where he often retires to write. See Kaufman, "This Upstate Retreat", August 26, 2018, Real Estate Section, 4, New York Edition.
- 2 Boccaccio's *Decameron* (1492) is structured around the telling of many stories by various characters who retreat to an isolated villa outside Florence to flee the Black Death. Chekhov's *Uncle Vanya* (1897) also deals with the country retreat of a retired professor, his young wife and daughter, and several other characters.
- 3 Secondary characters such as workmen, delivery people, or the SUV driver who stalks the premises, are described in the *Dramatis Personae* as "Various AMERICAN VILLAGERS". This label humorously invokes classic dramaturgical convention while foregrounding the contrast to the liberal bungalow colonists.
- 4 See Simon Rogers, "Gangnam Style", *The Guardian*, October 25, 2012, Shortcuts: Culture Section.
- 5 In *Lake Success*, the child's severe condition on the autistic spectrum seems partly inherited from Barry Cohen, his millionaire father, who displays a very similar social awkwardness to Ed Kim in *Our Country Friends*.
- 6 The reference is actually to Shteyngart's protagonist Misha in *Absurdistan*, which readers would remember as very self-centered. In his semi-autobiographical conception of Senderovsky, Shteyngart often explicitly draws on his own writing career.
- 7 He is only addressed by name once, at the very end, in a moment that seems to suggest an eventual recognition of his individual humanity: "'Joel', Dee said to him, 'Do you want to come down to the city?' He looked at her, mystified, as if she had never spoken his name aloud before" (*Friends* 297).
- 8 One such accusation involves a decontextualization of a student essay about *Gone With the Wind* to accuse her of racism. Shteyngart here targets the online campaigns of cancel culture, which function as a form of counter-narcissism inflicted by the divisiveness and polarization of social networks. See *Friends*, 195-7.
- 9 The burial of the manuscript is a symbolic act that suggests classic examples of censored or suppressed literature, such as Fyodor Dostoevsky's *Notes from the Underground* or Ralph Ellison's *Invisible Man*.
- 10 At the time of writing this article (May 2025), Gary Shteyngart had published a total of five novels. His sixth novel *Vera, or Faith* has since been published in July 2025.
- 11 The term's original meaning is clinical, and comes from Freud's psychoanalytical school, which differentiated the primary (typical) narcissistic phase of a child's development, from narcissism as a persisting, or "pathological" condition, in youth and into adulthood, defined by traits such as a sense of entitlement and self-importance, belief in success fantasies (of power, riches, beauty, ideal love), lack of empathy and instrumentalization of others, and a craving for admiration (see Peter Fonagy, Freud's "On Narcissism: An Introduction").

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[Address]

*Department of English, French and German
University of Vigo
Spain
urdiales@uvigo.gal*

Martín Urdiales-Shaw specializes in twentieth-century American Jewish literature, as well as contemporary literature, Holocaust literature, and literary translation, and has published extensively in the following fields: urban topographies, ethnicity and cultural identities, translation as cultural and textual representation and negotiation, language(s) and memorialization, waste studies, and globalization. His most outstanding publications include articles, book chapters and reviews on the works of Saul Bellow, Edward Dahlberg, Clifford Odets, Bernard Malamud, Henry Roth, Art Spiegelman, and Gary Shteyngart, with renowned international publishers such as Rodopi, Palgrave Macmillan, Taylor & Francis, Wayne State UP, Edinburgh UP, Oxford University Press, and Cambridge University Press. He has held the position of director of the Interuniversity Master's Programme in Advanced English Studies at the University of Vigo since 2021, and he currently serves as a member of the Executive Board of SAAS, the Spanish Association for American Studies.